

Surrogate load model / D2.1

WP2, T2.2

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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the development and demonstration of load surrogate models to be integrated as part of SUDOCO's "Control Room of The Future".

Traditional methods for estimating structural loads in wind farms require computationally expensive aero-servo-elastic simulations, limiting their feasibility for fast optimizations. To address this challenge, SUDOCO introduces these innovative location-agnostic and control-oriented surrogate models capable of efficiently predicting fatigue loads under varying operational conditions.

Four distinct surrogate modeling approaches were developed as part of SUDOCO, respectively by TUM, Shell, DTU, and TU Delft. While the presented method for generating the required synthetic data is common among all partners, each of the approaches leverages different methodologies for local inflow characterization and machine learning techniques for the surrogates. Concerning the choice of inputs of the surrogate to map the local inflow at a rotor disk, the different approaches include sector-averaged wind speed and turbulence intensity, velocity slices and proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) of the inflow. Concerning machine learning functions, the different approaches include shallow and deep artificial neural networks, random forest, as well as Gaussian process regression.

All of the surrogate models demonstrate high predictive accuracy, with strong agreement between predicted and actual damage equivalent loads (DELs) across both training and testing datasets. The POD-based surrogate reaches slightly higher accuracy than the others, at the cost of added complexity.

A parametric study further identifies optimal design choices for the surrogates, concerning the number of inputs to map the local inflow, the number of training points and the number of turbulence seeds required for robust performance. Across these three design criteria and four surrogate approaches, a crucial key finding is identified: there is a finite complexity that is sufficient to obtain converged performances for a general wind turbine load surrogate model.

Finally, the surrogates were successfully demonstrated in new wind farm cases and for new wind farm control actions, showcasing their ability to generalize beyond the training data. This achievement is a significant step toward enabling load-aware wind farm control and improving the overall efficiency and reliability of future offshore wind farms.

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1 Introduction

Wind farms suffer from wake effects that provoke a wind speed deficit and increased turbulence behind every turbine. In an array, downstream turbines consequently experience lower energy production and increased structural loads. Wind farm flow control (WFFC) consists of collaboratively regulating a cluster of turbines in order to increase its total performance (Meyers et al., 2022). The main strategies of WFFC include wake steering (intentionally misaligning the nacelle of upstream turbines to deflect their wake away from downstream ones) and static induction control (down-regulating the thrust of upstream turbines to reduce their wake). More recent and advanced methods include dynamic induction control (dynamically actuating the upstream turbines to enhance their wake recovery) as proposed in Frederik et al., 2020.

The first goal of WFFC has historically been to increase the power output of wind farms. This potential has been demonstrated not only numerically (Jiménez et al., 2010; Fleming et al., 2014; Vollmer et al., 2016), but also experimentally in the wind tunnel using scaled models (Medici and Alfredsson, 2006; Campagnolo et al., 2016; Schottler et al., 2017), as well as in full-scale field implementations (Fleming et al., 2019; Doekemeijer et al., 2021). However, the effect of WFFC on the structural loads of turbines remains unclear and is slowing down its large-scale industrial implementation. While the power output of any turbine in a wind farm can readily be estimated from fast steady-state wake models such as proposed by DTU, 2023; NREL, 2023, estimating the fatigue structural loads at the level of components requires computationally expensive aero-servo-elastic simulations on the wind farm level. This makes it infeasible to consider the loads for fast optimizations of wind farm layout or WFFC set-point optimizations.

For these reasons, the development of computationally efficient, yet accurate and generic, load surrogate models has become an area of increasing research interest, particularly for the synthesis of WFFC strategies beyond energy yield maximization (Dimitrov et al., 2018; Bossanyi, 2022). However, existing models tend to be either site-specific or fail to account for the complex effects of yaw misalignment and curtailment on both self-induced loads and the loads experienced by downstream turbines. As part of the SUDOCO research project, innovative methods of location-agnostic and control-oriented load surrogate models have been developed.

This deliverable presents the methods and results for four distinct load surrogate approaches in SUDOCO. They have respectively been developed by TUM, Shell, DTU and TU Delft. While these approaches have similarities in their broad range of

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applications, training and implementation; they differ in the choice of inputs to the surrogates and training functions. This collaborative report highlights their similarities and differences, with the goal of clarifying their methods for future replicability and implementations in this research project and others.

Chapter 2 starts with an extended review of past work on load surrogate modeling. The four new approaches developed in SUDOCO are then presented (Section 2.1), with their respective detailed methods for synthetic data generation (Section 2.2), processing into data to be used for load surrogates (Section 2.3) and finally the choice of training algorithms (Section 2.4). Chapter 2 also includes an extensive review of the missing elements in the current surrogate approaches, with notably floating loads (which effect is highlighted by quantitative inputs from the partner sowento in Section 2.5.2) and low-frequency fatigue cycles (Section 2.5.3).

Chapter 3 presents the results of the four proposed load surrogate approaches. First, key performance indicators over the whole training and testing data sets are highlighted (Section 3.1). Secondly, a parametric study on the influence of design choices on the surrogate performances is presented. The influence of the choice and number of inputs to characterize the local inflow is emphasized (Section 3.2.1), together with the number of training cases and number of turbulent seeds (Section 3.2.2). Lastly, the abilities of the surrogates to accurately predict loads based on unaccounted external parameters, new wind farm layout and new control actions are demonstrated using several examples (Section 3.3).

To conclude, Chapter 4 draws some final key outcomes on the methods and results of the newly developed load surrogates models, and draws recommendations for future improvements. Lastly, the link of these surrogate models with other work of the SUDOCO project is highlighted in order to build the holistic view of the “*Control Room of The Future*” towards integrated value-based operation of future offshore wind farms.

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2 Methods

Surrogate modeling of wind turbine loads is an ongoing area of research and development. The primary goal is to construct efficient load surrogate models capable of estimating fatigue loads with minimal computational cost, which can be integrated with steady-state engineering wake models. These models must balance accuracy and generality to ensure broad applicability, supporting wind farm control analysis including load-aware considerations. While various load surrogate modeling techniques have been proposed in the past, they often exhibit limitations and offer potential for further generalization. As part of the SUDOCO project, an extensive review of existing approaches has been conducted, alongside the development of new methodologies. This chapter provides a comprehensive review of prior work (Section 2.1.1) and an overview of the ongoing developments in the SUDOCO project (Section 2.1.2). Detailed specifications for the generation of relevant datasets (Section 2.2), their processing into key quantities (Section 2.3), and the training of straightforward yet effective load surrogate functions (Section 2.4) are presented. Lastly, current limitations and future directions are discussed in Section 2.5.

Globally, this chapter aims to present the latest approaches for wind turbine load surrogate modeling, as well as methodological guidelines for future replications and improvements of load surrogate models for any turbine type.

2.1 Review of load surrogate model approaches

2.1.1 Past work: What did load surrogates look like before SUDOCO?

In this section, notable works in the field of load surrogate modeling for wind farms are reviewed.

One of the first wind farm design frameworks including load constraints has been *TopFarm1*, described in Réthoré et al., 2014. In this work, the authors generated a load database using the *HAWC2* aero-elastic solver (Larsen et al., 2022) in addition to the Dynamic Meandering Model (DWM) based on Larsen et al., 2007. The dataset was based on the assumption that the wake, and in turn the fatigue loading, was dominated by the most upstream turbine. Therefore, only one turbine and one wake source needed to be simulated. This of course comes with huge limitations in the current perspective of building location-agnostic load surrogate models for application on any wind farm. In their work, the database was composed of the inflow

wind speed, ambient turbulence intensity, distance from the upstream wind turbine, and the angle between the line connecting the two turbines and the ambient wind velocity. Fatigue loading for each condition were obtained by 4D linear interpolation. A similar approach was used in *TopFarm2*, with the main difference that the look-up table was replaced by a neural network. A paper based on *TopFarm2* is Riva et al., 2020, which describes the Frandsen equivalent turbulence approach (Frandsen, 2007) instead of the DWM.

Several past works focused on a single turbine, instead of considering wind farm effects (thus missing the dominant effect of wakes on wind farm loadings, crucial for wind farm control applications in the current SUDOCO project). In particular, Murcia et al., 2018 trained a Polynomial Chaos Expansion (PCE) on a *HAWC2* database which depended on inflow conditions. Dimitrov et al., 2018 performed a similar study, but also trained: importance sampling, nearest-neighbor interpolation, universal Kriging (Krige, 1951), and quadratic response surface. Both Murcia et al., 2018 and Dimitrov et al., 2018 defined an input probability distribution and sampled it using quasi-random sequences, respectively (Hammersley, 1960) and (Halton, 1960). Although Kriging provides zero prediction error on the training set, it is also characterized by a rather slow prediction speed, because it requires populating a cross-correlation matrix (Dimitrov et al., 2018). During the development of *TopFarm2*, Kriging was considered too slow for wind farm design, and therefore Riva et al., 2020 used neural networks. In Murcia et al., 2015 it was observed that when the PCE is used to fit the power curve, it suffers from Runge's phenomenon, which causes unphysical oscillations in the (constant) full load region. This problem was ameliorated in Murcia et al., 2018 by applying the logistic transformation.

Neural networks were also explored by Dimitrov, 2019, with a focus on wake-induced fatigue loads. However, the proposed surrogate model was layout-dependent. Liew et al., 2023 presented a layout-agnostic surrogate model. In this paper, the flow field in front of each rotor is reduced to a few states via Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD). Then, a neural network is trained on the POD states to provide the fatigue loads. That paper also explored quadratic least-squares, which, although not as accurate as a neural network, provided decent accuracy and can be trained in a few seconds. The POD-based surrogate was later applied by Liew et al., 2024 to optimize the yaw of each turbine in a farm. Liew et al., 2023 also explored parametrizing the wake deficit via a skew normal distribution. Although more physics-based than the POD, this model was limited to one impinging wake, the training was slow and non-differentiable. An alternative approach was developed in Duthé et al., 2023 where the fatigue loads have been estimated through graph neural networks.

A big advancement towards wind farm level load surrogate modeling was made by Méndez Reyes et al., 2019. However, their approach was specific to a certain wind farm, requiring new training for a new wind farm. Another crucial work was pre-

sented by Bossanyi, 2022, who demonstrated the possibility of modeling wind turbine fatigue loads based on simple reduced-order inflow characterization. While this last work was demonstrated to be much more applicable than the previous works, it lacked the modeling of (partial-) wake effects as well as control actions on actuated and downstream wind turbines for a generic wind farm layout.

Based on these past works, the present deliverable presents load surrogate approaches that are tackling the need of location-agnostic and control-oriented generic load surrogate models for the purpose of load-aware wind farm control optimizations.

2.1.2 Methods developed in the SUDOCO project

As part of the SUDOCO project, several innovative approaches of location-agnostic and control-oriented load surrogates have been developed. This section provides an overview of the latest approaches covered.

Building a load surrogate model requires a number of design choices. Three main ones are the choice of dataset source (most typically from a simulation code, but can also be from scaled experiments or full size field measurements), the choice of inputs to the surrogate and the choice of surrogate function. Secondary choices include the number of input cases, number of turbulent seeds, and the scope application (with some wind farm control actions or not).

Four different approaches of load surrogate model have been developed as part of the SUDOCO project. Their main characteristics are summarized in Table 2.1, highlighting their similarities and differences.

All the proposed surrogates are location-agnostic. This means that a single surrogate function (typically per load channel) is applicable for any turbine, regardless of its position in a wind farm (upstream or (partially-)waked). The training dataset is created using a certain number of wind turbines (2 or 3) including the dynamic wake effects. But the surrogates can be applied to any new wind farm configuration (as long as the same turbine model is used). The surrogates have been tested on different open-source reference turbine models from the International Energy Agency (IEA). The IEA 22MW (Zahle et al., 2024) was selected to be used for the final case studies in the SUDOCO project. In that regard, all surrogate approaches will eventually be applied on this turbine. Prior work has originally developed the surrogates approaches on earlier turbine models: the IEA 3.4MW (Bortolotti et al., 2019) and the IEA 15MW (Gaertner et al., 2020). Changing the turbine type requires to run many new simulations to create a rich training dataset. But the surrogate approaches are universally applicable to any new turbine.

All the proposed surrogates are also control-oriented. This means that the effect of different control set-points are considered in the surrogate, in order to capture the effect of different wind farm control strategies on the fatigue load of actuated

Table 2.1: Characteristics of the load surrogate approaches developed in the SUDOCO project.

Main contributor	TUM (1)	Shell (2)	DTU (3)	TU Delft (4)
Simulation code	FAST.Farm	FAST.Farm	FAST.Farm	AMR-Wind/OpenFAST
Turbine model tested	IEA 3.4MW (Bortolotti et al., 2019), IEA 22MW (Zahle et al., 2024)	IEA 15MW (Gaertner et al., 2020), IEA 22MW (Zahle et al., 2024)	IEA 3.4MW (Bortolotti et al., 2019)	IEA 22MW (Zahle et al., 2024)
Number of turbines in training simulations	3	3	3	2/3
Location-agnostic?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Local inflow mapping	Sector-averaged WS and TI	Slices of velocity profiles	POD on WS and TI	Sector-averaged WS and TI
Other surrogate inputs	Pitch angle, rotor speed, yaw misalignment	Yaw misalignment	Pitch angle, rotor speed, yaw misalignment	Pitch angle, yaw misalignment
Control actions included	Yaw misalignment, curtailment	Yaw misalignment	Yaw misalignment, curtailment	Yaw misalignment, dynamic induction control
Number of training cases	30783 cases (IEA 3.4MW), 324 cases (IEA 22MW)	657 cases (IEA 22MW)	30783 cases (IEA 3.4MW)	8910 cases (IEA 22MW)
Number of turbulent seeds	24	12	24	6
Surrogate function	Shallow ANN	ANN, PCE, IDW, RBF, RMTB (past work); Random Forest	Deep ANN	Gaussian process
Published in	Guilloré et al., 2024, WESC 2025	Shaler et al., 2022	Liew et al., 2024 WESC 2025	WESC 2025

as well as downstream turbines. Static yaw misalignment for wake steering is the main wind farm control strategy, that all proposed surrogates include. Approaches (1) and (3) additionally include static curtailment (i.e. set-points of lower maximum power) in order to also consider static induction control. Approach (4) is considering an advanced dynamic induction control consisting of applying sinusoidal blade pitch signal to enhance wake mixing. For that reason, this approach required higher-fidelity simulations for the training dataset.

The surrogates differentiate themselves primarily by the choice of local inflow quantities at each rotor disk. This is indeed a key design choice for load surrogates: which local inflow characteristics are complex enough to capture the variation of fatigue loads in a wind farm, while simple enough to be easily available from a fast application perspective? While approach (2) use slices of velocity profiles at the rotor disk, approaches (1) and (4) are based on wind speeds and turbulence intensities averaged across sectors of the rotor disk. Finally, approach (3) applies proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) on the full turbulent field (wind speeds and turbulence intensities), to reduce into a few dominant modes.

Finally, the choice of surrogate function also differs for every approach. Approach (1) uses a shallow artificial neural network (ANN), composed of one layer of neurons. Approach (2) has been tested on a variety of surrogate functions: shallow ANN, polynomial chaos expansion (PCE), inverse distance weighting (IDW), radial basis functions (RBF), regularized minimal-energy tensor-product b-splines (RMTB) and random forests. Approach (3) uses deep ANN, composed of several layers of neurons. Finally, Approach (4) uses Gaussian processes.

The remainder of this chapter gives more insight into each of the approaches. While the results in Chapter 3 highlight similarities and differences in the performances of the surrogates.

Figure 2.1 depicts a high-level conceptual framework for various possible approaches of load surrogate modeling. The red background highlights the training and validation process. The blue background on the right illustrates the anticipated application of the surrogates. Offline optimizations using low-order inflow models can be used to build look-up tables of desired turbine set-points. Open-loop power boosting approaches such as presented for example in Meyers et al., 2022, could thus be complemented with the estimations of fatigue loads. The whole detailed application part will be covered by future deliverables of the SUDOCO project.

It is important to note that Fig. 2.1 aims to illustrate a generic approach for load surrogates. Block (a) could be replaced by any synthetic data generation from any dynamic aero-servo-elastic simulations, or scaled wind tunnel measurements, or full-scaled field measurements. The only requirements of Block (a) is to get measurements of 10min DELs and local inflow characterization to be used for the surrogate, as presented in Section 2.2. Block (b) can be replaced by any kind of reduced-order local inflow mapping in the post-processing step, as presented in Section 2.3. Block (c) can be replaced by any kind of adequate fitting surrogate functions as discussed in Section 2.4. Finally, the bottom of Fig. 2.1 illustrates the process for testing and assessing the performances of the load surrogates. Chapter 3 details on these results for all the four surrogate approaches considered.

Figure 2.1: Schematic overview of a generic approach for load surrogate modeling. The illustrations inside each block serve as exemplary purposes, but alternative approaches are discussed in this report.

2.2 Synthetic data generation

A number of requirements can be drawn for the generation of data to be used for the surrogates. This section details the methodology for generating synthetic data for the purpose of training and testing location-agnostic and control-oriented load surrogate models. The approaches of surrogate modeling can also readily be applied to experimental reduced-scaled or full-scaled measurements, as long as the required inputs and outputs of the surrogate can be obtained. However, up to now the surrogate approaches have been implemented with training and testing using synthetic data from simulations. For this reason, this section focuses on methods for synthetic data generation. Future work will focus on scaled and full-scale implementation of the surrogates.

2.2.1 Simulation set-up

The proposed approaches for location-agnostic and control-oriented surrogate model require data generation from aero-servo-elastic simulations on the wind farm level including dynamic wake effects. Indeed, the latter were shown to play a crucial role in assessing the structural fatigue loadings of turbines in a wind farm (Reinhardt et al., 2021; Kretschmer et al., 2021; Doubrawa et al., 2023).

Approaches (1), (2) and (3) use the simulation code FAST.Farm (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021; Kretschmer et al., 2021) to compute local inflow and structural loads at every turbine in a farm. This code combines OpenFAST simulation for each turbine instance with the dynamic wake meandering (DWM) model for solving the interaction between turbine due to wakes (Larsen et al., 2007). Fixed set-points of yaw misalignment and curtailment levels can be given to every turbine, and FAST.Farm captures their effect on actuated and downstream turbines. Conversely, the surrogate approach (4) is aimed at capturing the effects of advanced dynamic induction control, which are not covered by FAST.Farm. Thus, it uses the more computationally expensive code AMR-Wind (Sharma et al., 2024b) which is a CFD-based solver coupled with OpenFAST for structural computations.

Three turbines are used in each simulation. This allows to capture the wake effects and control actions of upstream turbines on the structural loads of the downstream ones. The first turbine is always in free-stream conditions and is actuated (yaw misalignment, curtailment or dynamic induction control). The second turbine both experiences a wake effect and can also be actuated. The third turbine experiences two wakes but is not actuated for wind farm control. This setup, using three turbines, is considered sufficient to capture all possible wake interactions while keeping computational costs reasonable. In fact, adding more turbines in the training simulations would likely not introduce new types of turbine-to-turbine interactions. All the surrogate approaches are location-agnostic, so in the post-processing step each turbine is considered as a separate entry for the training (local inflow quantities related to local structural loadings). The surrogates are not informed of the turbine position in a farm, as they aim to be applicable to any new wind farm layout and arbitrary location.

Various ambient wind conditions and farm-level configurations are run, as detailed in Table 2.2. As much variety as possible should be included in order for the surrogate to have a representative knowledge of all possible conditions. The bounds of the farm-level configurations should also be as wide as possible to allow for large application ranges of the surrogates (i.e. as data-driven approaches, the surrogates are only applicable in the range that they were trained on). The ranges are considered for application of wind farm control strategies, which are most typically applied below rated power of the turbines. For this reason, the hub-height velocity and yaw misalignment ranges are based on wake steering operational limits. The turbine spacing bounds are based on reference plant spacing. Other bounds are based on information in Wiley et al., 2023. To first focus on common turbine load channels and surrogate methodology development, hydrodynamic loads were not simulated.

Table 2.2: Boundaries of the parameter space for the training and testing of the surrogates.

Parameter	Ranges
Turbine spacing [D]	3-8
Hub-height velocity [m/s]	3-14
Shear exponent [-]	0-0.4
Inflow TI [%]	3.5-20
Wind direction [deg]	-/+ 20
Yaw misalignment [deg]	-/+ 30
Curtailement level [%]	5-100

2.2.2 Sampling method for input space

After defining the input, in terms of bounds or probability distribution, it is necessary to sample it. This can be done in two ways:

- **One shot:** the input database is generated once and kept constant for the simulations and surrogate model training.
- **Adaptive sampling:** the input database is constructed iteratively, by alternating phases of exploration and exploitation. During the exploration phase, new points are added where the surrogate error is largest, because of poorly resolved input domain or quick output variations. Instead, the exploitation phase aims at resolving those regions that are most critical, for example, where the loads are highest.

Pros and cons of the two approaches are described in table 2.3. The best workflow is to start from a one-shot strategy and then follow up with an adaptive sampling. The vast majority of articles in wind energy adopts the one-shot approach. One article that used adaptive sampling is Santhanam et al., 2023. In the following, we will focus on the one shot. one-shot methods balance two conflicting requirements:

Table 2.3: Pros and cons of the one-shot and adaptive sampling approaches.

	Pros	Cons
One shot	Simple	No control over the prediction error. Adding new points can be difficult.
Adaptive sampling	Effective for reducing the prediction error. Optimal usage of computational resources.	Requires ad hoc software.

- Have high space filling, which means that points should densely cover the whole input domain.
- Do not add points that have little effect on the output. For example, because the output is flat in a certain region, or because the Weibull distribution implies that they will have little impact on the lifetime loads.

Some sampling strategies, with pros and cons are listed in table 2.4. In light of the pros and cons, the selected methodology for the one-shot approach is:

- Use OpenTURNS (Baudin et al., 2016) to generate the input database. This is because it has an outstanding modeling of probability distributions and several methods to draw the points.
- Define the probability distribution for the uncoupled variables, like wind shear and air density.
- Define the probability distribution for the coupled variables, like wind speed and turbulence intensity.
- Draw the points for the uncoupled variables using a Halton sequence with scrambling.
- Draw the points for the coupled variables using the Latin hypercube.

This way, thousands of points can be generated in seconds on a common laptop. The input probability distribution is arbitrary, which allows to optimize the computational cost (within the limits of the one-shot approach).

Another implemented approach is to use Latin Hypercube Sampling (LHS) to sample the input parameter space. This is a near-random sampling technique that ensures all areas of a multidimensional space are evenly represented. A 3-dimensional representation of this is shown in Figure 2.2, but all parameters listed in Table 2.2 were sampled with this technique.

The benefits of using a random sampling technique, as opposed to a gridded one, is that it provides more representative combinations of the parameter space and therefore often requires fewer simulations to reach a converged surrogate model.

2.2.3 Aero-servo-elastic modelling

All surrogate generation requires aero-servo-elastic simulations to be performed. Most participants (Shell, TUM, and DTU) used FAST.Farm to perform these simulations. FAST.Farm is a multiphysics engineering tool that accounts for wake interaction effects on turbine performance and structural loading within wind farms (Jonkman

Table 2.4: Pros and cons of the one-shot sampling strategies.

	Pros	Cons
Mesh grid	Best space filling strategy. Makes plotting easy (no need to train a surrogate)	Maximum computational cost. Suffers the most from the curse of dimensionality. Adding just one new level in a feature requires adding an entirely new hyper-plane. Might generate nonphysical conditions (like high turbulence intensity at high wind speed).
Monte Carlo	Simple and cheaper than mesh grid, especially for adding new points. Less sensitive to the curse of dimensionality. Fast generation. Allows probability distribution.	Points are too random, and sometimes they end up too close or far from each other.
Latin hypercube	Same as Monte Carlo. Points are random within each cube, which improves space filling.	It requires a lot of points to achieve the assigned probability distribution.
Quasi-random sequence (Halton)	The input domain is uniformly filled. It requires fewer points than the Latin hypercube to achieve the assigned probability distribution. Fast generation if the input probability distribution has independent features.	Too slow if the input probability distribution has dependent features. Points becomes correlated when there are many features (scrambling ameliorates this).

Figure 2.2: 3-dimensional representation of LHS sampling used in surrogate generation.

and Shaler, 2021). FAST.Farm extends the National Renewable Energy Laboratory's OpenFAST tool, which solves the aero-hydro-servo-elasto dynamics of individual turbines, to include wake deficits, advection, deflection, meandering, and merging for wind farms. Ambient wind inflow is generated synthetically using TurbSim (Jonkman, 2016), which creates two-dimensional turbulent flow planes that are convected through the domain with the freestream velocity. Turbulence is simulated using the Kaimal spectrum and exponential coherence model. (Shaler et al., 2022) Turbulent inflows were generated for all of the parametric inflow conditions, with a varying number of seeds.

FAST.Farm is suitable for generating training data under normal operating conditions, wake steering, or curtailment. However, wake-mixing control strategies that require high pitch actuation such as the Helix method (Frederik et al., 2020), are not accurately modeled within FAST.Farm. To generate the necessary training data, an alternative simulation approach was adopted by TUD using the Large-Eddy Simulation (LES) code AMR-Wind (Sharma et al., 2024a). The inflow conditions for the LES were generated by precursor simulations of a conventionally neutral boundary layer with hub-height wind speeds ranging between $U_\infty = 6\text{--}10$ m/s, and with a turbulence intensity of approximately 4%. The wind turbines were modelled using the actuator line method (ALM), which applies the body forces from the wind turbine blades to the incoming flow. The body forces are in turn determined through a coupling with the aeroelastic solver OpenFAST. The LES simulations were run for different operational conditions (i.e. normal operation, the helix method with multiple pitch amplitudes, and wake steering for positive and negative yaw misalignments)

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Figure 2.3: Illustration of the simulation set-up in FAST.Farm (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021) used for synthetic data generation for the surrogate approaches (1), (2) and (3). The illustrated case corresponds to a turbine spacing of $6D$, wind direction -5° , ambient wind speed at 10m/s and $TI\ 6\%$

and using either 1 or 3 turbines to consider different wake conditions.

2.3 Processing into data to be used for a load surrogate

Once the aero-servo-elastic simulations are run, time series of channels of interest are post-processed into quantities to be used for the load surrogates. These are the outputs of interest, the damage equivalent loads (DELs); and the inputs for the surrogates, that are reduced-order quantities to characterize the local inflow at each rotor and control parameters. Both these outputs and inputs are averaged over all the turbulent seeds in order to ensure convergence of the statistics. The method to convert time series of loads into 10min DELs (Sect. 2.3.1) is common across the four surrogate approaches, in order to predict the same quantities. The surrogates differs in their choice of local inflow quantities as inputs (see Sect. 2.3.2).

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Figure 2.4: Schematic representation of load surrogate framework for predicting loads with wake-mixing techniques (Approach (4)).

2.3.1 Damage Equivalent Loads (DELs)

Four load channels are considered in this work (but the methods of the surrogate is applicable to any available load measurements), using projection along the maximum damage direction. For each time series, the 10min DEL is computed using a conventional rainflow counting and the formula:

$$DEL = \left(\frac{\sum (n_i L_i^m)}{N_{eq}} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}}, \quad (2.1)$$

where n_i is the number of load cycles of amplitude L_i , N_{eq} is the equivalent number of cycles (taken as per convention at $2e6$ cycles over a lifetime of 20 years), and m is the Wöhler exponent of the S-N curve of the material (chosen as $m = 10$ for the polymer material of the blades and $m = 4$ for the steel material of the main shaft and tower) as prescribed in IEC 61400-1, 2019; Sutherland, 1999.

For each of the load locations listed below, and at each time step, the two orthogonal components of a given load are projected along all possible directions, with an angular step of 10° . All corresponding DELs are computed using Eq. (2.1), and the maximum value is then stored as the “*projected DEL*.” This projection is necessary to identify the most damaged direction on each cross-section. The considered projected load channels and their components are:

- “**Blade root DEL**”: blade root in-plane and out-of-plane bending moments.
- “**Shaft DEL**”: shaft out-of-plane and yaw bending moments.
- “**Yaw bearings DEL**”: tower top fore-aft and side-side bending moments.

- **“Tower base DEL”**: tower bottom fore-aft and side-side bending moments.

2.3.2 Local inflow mapping

The location-agnostic surrogates are built on the knowledge of local inflow characterization. From the aero-servo-elastic simulations, time series of wind velocities across each rotor disk are post-processed into reduced order quantities. The main objective when designing a load surrogate model is to find suitable inflow quantities that are complex enough to capture the complex trends of DELs, while being simple enough to be obtainable from a reduced-order (steady-state) modeling tool for fast application in optimizations problems as in DTU, 2023; NREL, 2023. The four surrogate approaches mainly differentiate themselves by this choice of local inflow characterization.

Sector-averaged inflow mapping

TUM’s approach (1) is based on sector-averaged mean wind speeds and turbulence intensities across the rotor disk (Guilloré et al., 2024). The cyclic variations of structural loads fundamentally create the DELs of a wind turbine as the rotor is spinning (space dependency) and the turbulent wind field is varying (time dependency). Therefore, DELs depend not only on the rotor-averaged wind speed but also predominantly on the spatio-temporal variation of this wind speed across the rotor disk. Previous work demonstrated that relying solely on rotor-averaged wind speeds is not sufficient to adequately capture DELs (Liew et al., 2023). In a wind farm, wake effects significantly amplify this spatio-temporal variation (due to local speed deficits and dynamic wake meandering). The present surrogate formulation employs four sector-averaged wind speeds (SAWS) to capture spatial variability at the rotor disk. Additionally, it uses sector-averaged turbulence intensities (SATI) to capture temporal variability (and its coupling with spatial variation). Introducing higher-order inflow quantities, such as an increased number of sectors or refined statistics, has the potential to enhance the informational content for predicting DELs. However, obtaining these higher-order quantities for fast surrogate application may increase complexity and computational cost, and their use may lead to overfitting the training points. The testing of various number of sectors at the rotor disk and their impact on the performances of the surrogate is reported in Fig. 3.7 and Fig. 3.8. Four sectors and their SAWS and SATI proved sufficient to deliver the desired accuracy.

Various techniques can be employed to estimate local SAWS and SATI, enhancing the broad applicability of the surrogate approach:

- In dynamic numerical simulations: utilizing virtual flow sensors at specific locations (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021). This approach is illustrated on Fig. 2.5 and it is the one that is used in the results presented in this report.

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Figure 2.5: Method for extracting four sector-averaged wind speeds (SAWS) and turbulence intensities (SATI) from rotating virtual sensors on the blades in dynamic numerical simulations.

- In steady-state engineering flow models: estimating local wind speeds and turbulence intensities, as shown in DTU, 2023; NREL, 2023. These inflow models are able to estimate the SAWS and SATI, defined as steady-state quantities that are averaged over time and a sufficient number of turbulent seeds.
- In the field:
 - ground-based or nacelle-mounted lidar can estimate the spatio-temporal wind field (Meyers et al., 2022).
 - wind observers can be used to estimate local inflow quantities based on the measurement of blade root loads as shown in (Bottasso et al., 2018; Schreiber et al., 2020).

It is clear that each one of these techniques provides the SAWS and SATI only within a certain level of accuracy. In turn, this only limited accuracy will affect the quality of the surrogate and of its estimates.

Velocity plane slices

In Shell's approach (2), the potential surrogate input parameters are the velocity components at vertical, horizontal, and $\pm 45^\circ$ slices across the rotor plane. These slices are shown in Figure 2.6(c) on top of the time-averaged T1 rotor plane u-velocity. Standard deviations and absolute maximum values were also considered,

Figure 2.6: Inflow statistics generation process. (a) Time-averaged results vs azimuthal angle; (b) Time- and azimuthally-averaged results vs spatial location; (c) inflow rotor plane and velocity profile "slice" visualization. Shaler et al., 2022

resulting in three potential temporal statistics. Sampling the rotor plane velocity field in FAST.Farm is most easily done by exporting the instantaneous inflow wind velocity of all 50 blade stations at each time step. These values neglect blade and induced velocity effects, and are purely the inflow values including any wake effects from upstream turbines. Then, for each blade station (radial position), the data is binned into 5° segments by the corresponding azimuthal position, as depicted in Figure 2.6(a). Here, each line shows the time-averaged value at each azimuthal angle for a given blade station. From here, the time-averaged planar velocity across varying rotor plane cross sections can be constructed by pulling out the values at specific azimuthal angles. For example, the horizontal rotor plane cross section is taken to be the time-averaged values from Figure 2.6(a) at 270° and 90° (0° is the blade pointing vertically up), as shown in Figure 2.6(b). This same process is repeated for the vertical cross section (0° and 180°); $+45^\circ$ cross section (225° and 45°); and -45° cross section (315° and 135°). On each slice, first, second, and third spatial moments of the velocity components are computed. The three velocity

components, four slices, three temporal statistics, and three spatial moments give 108 possible turbine-inflow values to be used as input dimensions (Shaler et al., 2022). This process was initially developed and tested in Shaler et al., 2022.

Proper Orthogonal Decomposition for Flow Parameterisation

In DTU's approach (3), Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is used to identify the dominant patterns in a complex, high-dimensional dataset, providing an efficient representation of the inflow field. The advantage of using POD for parameterizing the flow, rather than relying on classical rotor averaged wind speed and turbulence intensity, is that POD preserves the spatial variability of the inflow across the rotor plane, which is lost while using a rotor averaged quantities especially when there is a velocity deficit causing partial or full wake on the downstream turbine. The different flow conditions considered in this study, including free flow, partial wake and full wake are illustrated in Figure 2.7. This research extends the approach in Liew et al., 2024 by applying POD to both wind speed and turbulence intensity over the rotor plane, whereas the original study applies POD only to wind speed data and characterised turbulence using standard deviation of the wind speed at the hub height. By directly incorporating the turbulence intensity in the POD, this method provides a more detailed characterisation of the wind field. Unlike the approach in Liew et al., 2024, which extracts wind speed inflows over a fine 30×30 Cartesian grid, this study uses a coarser 9×36 polar grid as shown in Figure 2.7. The adequacy of this resolution is supported by recent results in Guilloré et al., 2024, which demonstrated, despite the lower grid resolution, surrogate models trained using sector-averaged quantities computed from 9×36 grids still achieved good predictive performance.

Figure 2.7: Visualisation of the 9×36 polar grid showing different flow conditions across the rotor plane. The three subplots represents different flow cases, illustrating the spatial variability of wind speed distribution.

The flow field data matrix \mathbf{F} for the POD is constructed in such a way that each column corresponds to the wind field, and turbulence intensity of a unique turbine in

a wind farm.

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}_1 & \mathbf{f}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{f}_{n_x} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{U}\mathbf{\Sigma}\mathbf{V}^T \quad (2.2)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_i = \left[[u_1 \ u_2 \ \dots \ u_p]^T, [ti_1 \ ti_2 \ \dots \ ti_p]^T \right]$ represents the inflow of a particular turbine. The u and ti component correspond to wind speed, and turbulence intensity, respectively, for a specific flow case \mathbf{f}_i . Here, p denotes the total number of spatial locations in the polar grid. The matrices \mathbf{U} , $\mathbf{\Sigma}$, and \mathbf{V} in Eq. (2.2) represent the spatial modes, the singular values indicating the energy of each mode, and the parametric variations, respectively. The decomposition of \mathbf{F} was computed using randomised singular value decomposition (SVD), which is well suited for efficiently computing singular vectors as demonstrated by Andersen and Murcia Leon, 2022, particularly for high-dimensional datasets such as the one in this study. The original flow field can be parameterised using a small number of modes as already shown by Liew et al., 2023. To ensure an optimal reduced-order representation, the wind speed and turbulence intensity field in flow matrix \mathbf{F} were independently normalised. Specifically, the wind speed components u were scaled by dividing by the maximum wind speed, while turbulence intensity components ti were scaled by dividing by the maximum turbulence intensity. Through an explained variance analysis, it was determined that 11 modes were sufficient to capture 99.99% of the variance in the data. The parameterised flow of a particular turbine can be obtained through $\hat{\mathbf{f}}_i = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{f}_i$, and parameterising the entire flow matrix is as simple as $\hat{\mathbf{F}} = \mathbf{U}_r^T \mathbf{F}$ where \mathbf{U}_r represents the first r dominant modes of \mathbf{U} . To assess the effectiveness of the reduced order representation, reconstruction of a reference flow case \mathbf{f}_x was performed using different number of modes, as shown in Figure 2.8. When using only a single mode, a significant loss of information occurs, leading to a high reconstruction error. As the number of modes increases, the reconstruction error decreases rapidly within the first few modes and converges quickly around 5 modes.

Figure 2.8: Reconstruction of a reference flow case f_x from original flow matrix F using different number of modes.

Extraction of sector-averaged inflow quantities from the LES simulations

In TUD's approach (4), cross-stream flow slices incorporating three velocity components were exported from the LES at a frequency of 1 Hz at distances ranging from $3D-8D$ downstream. These flow slices were divided into 10-minute sequences, representing multiple turbulence seeds. By shifting these flow slices laterally, varying inflow conditions, such as free stream, partial wake overlap, and full wake overlap, could be considered. The flow slices were then converted to wind data input compatible with OpenFAST to generate the loads database. The inflow sampling process is visualized in Figure 2.9. The wind input files were subsequently processed to acquire sector-averaged wind speed and turbulence intensity maps (Guilloré et al., 2024) to be used in the surrogate model.

2.3.3 Other inputs required for load surrogates

The local inflow quantities mentioned above are defined "as if the turbine was not there". That is, they are not influenced by the operational state of the turbine. In addition to the local inflow, the way that a rotor is controlled is playing an important role in the structural loading of the turbines. To incorporate the effect of wake steering actuation, the yaw misalignment angle is included as an additional input to the surrogate in all four approaches. In approaches (1) and (3), the 10-min mean rotor speed and blade pitch angle are also included as inputs to the surrogate, to capture the effect of curtailment (for static induction control). Finally, the surrogate approach (4) includes the blade pitch amplitude to capture the effect of dynamic

Figure 2.9: Example of a cross-stream slice of the velocity field extracted from the LES. The circle represents the rotor area of the upstream turbine. The velocity field is sampled at the grid locations and then converted to an OpenFAST input file. By shifting the grid laterally, we can simulate different wake conditions.

induction control.

2.4 Load surrogate functions and training algorithms

Once the dataset is constructed, it is randomly shuffled before being split in two to create training and testing subsets. Shuffling ensures similar distributions between both subsets.

TUM (1) uses the Matlab Deep Learning toolbox (The MathWorks, 2021) for the creation and training of a shallow Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The mean of squared errors is minimized using hyperbolic tangent sigmoid activation functions and Bayesian regularization. The ANN comprises 1 layer with 30 neurons. The training takes a wall time of only 1 min approximately. Once it is trained, the ANN is expressed as a simple mathematical function that can be evaluated in a fraction of a second. Such short evaluation times enable complex optimization-based applications, such as farm layout design and farm control.

Shell (2) uses internal software to generate their surrogate models. While many surrogate model options are available, they chose to use a random forest method for speed and simplicity. Future work could include ANN methods. The random forest surrogate method starts by implementing a median/mode imputation, that is further refined using random forest fits. This method is often recommended for datasets with nonlinear relationships and multiple interaction effects compared to simpler imputation techniques or outright deletion (AutoSum, 2025). At present, all results using this software must be generated from the software. There is an option to export the models to a python-readable format; however, this has not been done

yet.

DTU (3) uses a fully connected neural network (FCNN) as the surrogate model to capture non-linear relationship between inputs and outputs. The choice of FCNN is motivated by its ability to handle high-dimensional input spaces, such as spatially varying flows used in this study. Unlike kernel-based methods which often struggle with high-dimensional data, FCNN effectively handles high-dimensional input space by automatically learning relevant features, reducing the need for extensive manual feature engineering. Additionally, the prediction time using FCNN is lower than kernel-based methods. Unlike kernel methods, which require computing similarity measures with all training samples, FCNN performs a single forward pass with matrix multiplication and activation functions. This makes the prediction process of a FCNN highly efficient for large datasets.

The implementation was done using TensorFlow with Keras for model development, and optuna for hyperparameter tuning. The inputs to the surrogates are the reduced-order representation $\hat{\mathbf{F}}$ along with other control inputs mentioned in the table 2.1. In contrast to Liew et al., 2023, where control parameters were excluded in the surrogate modelling process, this work incorporates them to account for variations in operating conditions. To improve the training process, both inputs and outputs were standardized to have zero mean and unit variance. The dataset was randomly split into three subsets following a 70:10:20 ratio, where 70% of the data was employed for training, 10% for validation - used exclusively for hyperparameter tuning, and 20% for testing.

A total of 120 different hyperparameter configurations were tested for each load surrogates, optimising the number of layers in the FCNN, the number of neurons per layer, and the activation function. Optuna was used to tune all three, selecting between Exponential Linear Unit (ELU) and hyperbolic tangent (Tanh) for the activation function. These activation functions were specifically chosen because both ensures smooth and differentiable surrogate models. Although both activation functions were explored, ELU consistently outperformed Tanh across all trained surrogates. For training, the Adam algorithm was used due to its efficient adaptive learning rate and momentum based updates, which improves convergence speed. Additionally, Optuna employed the Tree-Structured Parzen Estimator algorithm for efficient hyperparameter tuning. Furthermore, the parameters to points ratio across all models remains below 0.3, ensuring that the model complexity was appropriately controlled and minimising the overfitting problem.

TUD (4) employs Gaussian process regression (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006) to infer DELs from wind speed and TI input data. The sector-averaged inflow mapping proposed by TUM was adopted for this model (Guilloré et al., 2024). The Gaussian process assumes that a set of noisy load measurements, expressed in DELs, belong to a multivariate Gaussian distribution that is a function of the

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sector-averaged inflow. The correlation between different input locations is determined through a covariance matrix. For this study, we implemented the widely used squared-exponential covariance function. Training the load surrogate model consists of tuning a set of hyperparameters, one for each input, one for the output, and one representing the measurement noise. Prior to training, the input and output data is normalized to have zero mean and unit variance. The hyperparameters are then tuned by maximizing the marginal likelihood (Rasmussen and Williams, 2006). Inference for a given set of inflow conditions then consists of a mean load prediction, as well as the variance around the predicted mean. In short, a Gaussian process provides a measure of uncertainty to the prediction. A high uncertainty could indicate a noisy dataset, or insufficient training data at the input location.

2.5 Missing elements in existing surrogate approaches and future work

2.5.1 Ultimate loads

Ultimate loads are an important consideration for wind farm design and operation, and the surrogate techniques described in this document would be capable of capturing such responses. Indeed, ultimate loads are available from the training simulation dataset. New surrogate functions can readily be trained to predict ultimate loads instead of fatigue loads based on the same inputs. However, this work is focused on wind farm control. Because of this, only normal operation is considered (with some curtailment), and no extreme changes are included. Under these conditions, the driving design cases would all be from fatigue loading. Therefore, ultimate loads are not considered in this work, but would be an important consideration to extend the generality of this work.

2.5.2 Fatigue loads for floating application (sowento)

The surrogate load models discussed in the previous sections have been developed specifically for bottom-fixed offshore wind turbines. While sea states and wave loads are not entirely negligible for these foundations, they are irrelevant to modeling the dependence of the fatigue damage of multiple components, e.g., tower base DELs or blade root DELs (cf. Section 2.3.1), on rotor inflow.

In contrast, floating foundations introduce several additional considerations. Firstly, there are extra components for which lifetime analysis is essential, most notably the mooring lines. Secondly, the system response and the loads on various components – such as tower base loads – can change significantly for a floating turbine. Therefore, we want to highlight some important considerations to be taken into account when developing surrogate models for structural loads for floating offshore

wind turbines.

SOW utilized the platform definition provided with the bottom-fixed IEA 22MW offshore reference wind turbine (Zahle et al., 2024). This platform is a steel semisubmersible featuring three outer columns, three pontoons, and a central main column supporting the tower. Due to the added complexity introduced by the hydrodynamic and mooring line models, a full surrogate model was not developed at this stage. Instead, a sensitivity study was conducted to analyze the system's response to varying inflow conditions and sea state.

In this study, we examined a wide range of wind and sea state conditions: reference wind speeds u from 5 to 20 m/s in steps of 1 m/s, standard deviations of the incoming wind turbulence σ_1 from 1 to 5 m/s, and waves with a JONSWAP spectrum with periods T_p of 7, 9, 11, and 13 s and significant wave heights H_s from 1 to 5 m.

Figure 2.10 shows the distribution of the inflow turbulence, quantified by the standard deviation σ_1 , over the mean wind speed. It can be observed that the range of points is far larger than the ranges covered by the four turbulence categories defined in IEC 61400-1, 2019. This is to cover a broad range of conditions possibly experienced by downwind turbines affected by the wake of an upstream turbine. The inflow wind fields are generated using TurbSim (Jonkman, 2016).

Figure 2.10: Distribution of the wind speed standard deviation σ_1 over the mean wind speed for the floating offshore wind turbine study. The crosses indicate combinations of wind speed and σ_1 that were used to generate turbulent inflow conditions, the lines indicate the distributions of σ_1 according to the turbulence categories defined in IEC 61400-1, 2019.

A total of 1,600 simulations were performed, each with a duration of 4,000 seconds, including an initial transient period of 400 seconds. To reduce computational effort, a simplified aerodynamic model was employed, using a lookup table for rotor power and thrust coefficients as functions of tip speed ratio and blade pitch angle. Additionally, mooring line forces were represented using a quasi-static lookup table. While previous studies (Azcona et al., 2017) indicate that a quasi-static mooring model may significantly underestimate the DEL of fairlead tensions for semisubmersible platforms, this approach is considered sufficiently accurate for evaluating trends across different environmental conditions. The computation of the DEL and the parameters used for the tower base load DEL are described in Section 2.3.1. For the computation of the fairlead tension DEL the Wöhler exponent is set to $m = 3$ and the number of cycles is set to $5e7$.

Figure 2.11 shows the distribution of the upwind mooring fairlead DEL at a wind speed of 10 m/s for different sea states. It can be observed that, while increases in the significant wave height H_s and wave period T_p lead to slightly higher DEL, the main driver behind the increase in DEL is the incoming wind turbulence. Figure 2.12

Figure 2.11: Distribution of the fairlead 1 tension DEL across multiple inflow turbulence and sea state variations.

compares the tower base load DEL with the upwind mooring fairlead tension DEL, illustrating how the additional load channel for floating turbines, i.e., the fairlead tensions, responds to variations in inflow turbulence and sea state, compared to a load channel also used for bottom-fixed turbines, i.e., the tower base loads.

Several observations can be made: Generally, an increase in inflow turbulence raises the DEL for both load channels. However, for many sea states (e.g., $T_p = 9$ s, $H_s = 5$ m), the tower base DEL increase is moderate under higher inflow turbulence, whereas the fairlead tension DEL can increase more than threefold. Moreover, an increase in the wave height leads to an increase in the tower base DEL for all shown cases, but the fairlead tension DEL is sometimes even reduced for higher wave heights.

Figure 2.12: Distribution of the tower base load DEL and fairlead 1 tension DEL across multiple inflow turbulence and sea state variations.

In conclusion, the transition from a bottom-fixed to a floating foundation not only increases the number of critical load channels but also greatly expands the parameter space. While the dependence of fatigue on disturbed inflow conditions is already complex for bottom-fixed turbines, it becomes substantially more complex for floating turbines. Consequently, a full surrogate model for a floating foundation would need to be trained with a large variation in sea states.

It is noted that second-order difference-frequency wave loads are expected to have a significant contribution to fairlead tension fatigue. This effect is not considered in this study because the required Quadratic Transfer Functions (QTF) or mean drift coefficients are not yet available for the 22MW design at the time of writing. The authors expect a comparable influence as for the turbulence intensity. However, the wave period can have an effect, which depends on the floater hull shape.

The wind turbine controller is known to have a significant effect on fairlead tension fatigue. Here, the IEA22MW reference ROSCO controller is used (Zahle et al., 2024). This controller might not be optimally tuned yet as it is at a conceptual stage. The controller can also have nonlinear influences on the wind and wave response.

2.5.3 Low-frequency fatigue cycles

The surrogate load models discussed so far are based on a typical fatigue assessment that follows a statistical approach by binning 10-minute wind and operating conditions over the lifetime of a wind turbine. However, such a fatigue assessment fails to completely account for the low-frequency fatigue cycles (LFFCs) due to their statistical nature. While LFFCs arising from transitions between operating modes are partially accounted for, cycles due to wind variations longer than the typical 10-minute intervals such as low-frequency turbulence, diurnal cycles, seasonal changes are completely ignored in a standard fatigue assessment. These cycles exhibit high stress ranges and have a significant impact on the estimated lifetime of wind turbine components (Sadeghi et al., 2022). While a time-marching approach would easily incorporate LFFCs, it can be significantly more expensive than the standard approach. Ongoing work is being carried out to extend the present surrogate approaches towards a model for LFFCs. It is planned to parametrize the LFFCs as minimum value, maximum value and number of residuals in the rainflow counting of 10-min intervals. If appears necessary, probabilistic distributions of these residuals are also envisioned to be predicted by such an extended surrogate. Following similar approach, these new quantities will be predicted based on the 10-minute environmental and operating conditions.

This work is in development and it is outside of the scope of the surrogates presented here. The surrogates presented in this deliverable are to be used for wind farm control applications, which were shown to have a small influence on the LFFCs. However, future applications can encompass this limitation to have a more complete picture on lifetime damage considering low-frequency variations in wind conditions.

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3 Results

This chapter presents results of the four load surrogate approaches presented in Table 2.1, whose methods were detailed in Sect. 2.2 and Sect. 2.3. First, key performance indicators evaluated across the whole training and testing subsets are presented in Sect. 3.1, for the four proposed formulation of surrogates. Secondly, Sect. 3.2 extends on a parametric study for the best design choices to build a load surrogate: selection and number of inputs and number of training points necessary for convergence. Finally, Sect. 3.3 showcases the abilities of the surrogates to capture the trends of DELs by unaccounted external parameters and for a new wind farm configuration.

3.1 Key performance indicators for the load surrogates

Surrogate model performance was measured by comparing the predicted load channel statistic against the actual value at every point in both the training and the testing datasets. For this vector of comparison values, accuracy was quantified using the classical r^2 correlation coefficient, the root mean squared errors (RMSE) and the root mean square percentage error (RMSPE). The r^2 correlation coefficient measures the linear dependence between two variables and is therefore a useful measure of how well the surrogate tracks the trend of the truth values. The average percent error was used as the most intuitive measure of accuracy, although artificially large errors are predicted when the truth values are small (Shaler et al., 2022).

3.1.1 Sectors-based surrogate approach (TUM (1))

Figure 3.1 presents the training and testing results of the four ANNs for the projected blade root, shaft, yaw bearing, and tower base DELs using the sector-based approach applied to the IEA 3.4MW turbine (Guilloré et al., 2024). It is important to note that the data from all three wind turbines are mixed together (the surrogate not being informed of the turbine position). Overall, minimal scatter is observed, confirming the validity of this surrogate approach. The resulting RMSPE are relatively low compared to other surrogate approaches (Dimitrov, 2019; Méndez Reyes et al., 2019; Bossanyi, 2022). The surrogate for blade root DEL performs the best, with a validation RMSPE value of only 0.48%. The surrogates for the shaft and yaw bearing DELs also perform very well with a validation RMSPE value of around 2%. The surrogate for tower base DELs shows more outliers. This component is the

most sensitive to stochastic wind turbulence fluctuations. Nevertheless, the surrogate performs quite well with a validation RMSPE value of only 3.21%. Importantly, all validation RMSPE values are not significantly higher than the training RMSPE values, indicating avoidance of overfitting and a general applicability to new cases.

Figure 3.1: Scatter plots of the training and validation subsets resulting from the ANNs training for the four considered DELs (all three wind turbines) using the sector-based surrogates. Root-mean-square percentage errors (RMSPE) values are indicated. These surrogates are trained on 50% of the 30783 cases using the IEA 3.4MW turbine.

Figure 3.2 presents the results of the same sector-based surrogate approach applied to the new IEA 22MW wind turbine (Zahle et al., 2024). A large data set is currently in development. These first surrogates include 108 finished FAST.Farm cases (i.e. 324 cases of local inflow to DELs considering the three turbines). A slightly higher scatter is observed, especially for the test data set. This is due to the low number of training points at this stage, which is expected to be improved by incorporating more points in the near future. Nevertheless, the surrogate performs reasonably well, demonstrating the applicability of this sector-based surrogate to a new wind turbine (completely different from the aero-servo-elastic design perspective).

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Figure 3.2: Scatter plots of the training and validation subsets resulting from the ANNs training for the four considered DELs (all three wind turbines) using the sector-based surrogates. Root-mean-square percentage errors (RMSPE) values are indicated. These surrogates are trained on 50% of the 324 cases using the IEA 22MW turbine.

3.1.2 Surrogate based on inflow velocity slices (Shell (2))

Shown in Figure 3.3 are scatter plots comparing predicted and actual results for surrogate models generated using slices of turbine inflow velocity planes. The top row shows results for low-speed shaft torque DELs and the bottom row for yaw bearing roll moment DELs. The purpose of this figure is to show the impact of including or excluding certain input parameters. In particular, the first column (Figures 3.3 (a) and (d)) shows results where the nacelle yaw was not included as an input when generating the surrogates. While good agreement was seen for most outputs (overall 0.9-0.98), some outputs showed very poor performance, in particular the yaw bearing roll moment DELs ($r^2 = 0.41$). However, when nacelle yaw was included as input, the surrogate accuracy for all inputs increased, in particular that for the yaw bearing roll moment ($r^2 = 0.98$), as seen when comparing Figures 3.3(d) and (e). Additionally, it is observed in Figure 3.3(a) that there seems to be a correlation between nacelle yaw (the color of the points) and distance off the diagonal, indicating that a higher error is shown for higher nacelle yaw. However, when nacelle yaw is included as an input, this relationship is no longer apparent, shown in Figure 3.3(b) and (c).

Given the high number of available input parameters, and the potential limited availability from a future application (e.g. FLORIS NREL, 2023), it is of interest to determine what input parameters are necessary to include. To explore this, correlations between the variables were computed, as well as importance parameter plots. Based on these results, the number of relevant input parameters across all outputs was reduced from 109 to 34, including nacelle yaw. In particular, due to a mixture of correlation and importance, all temporal standard deviation and absolute maximum inputs for the y - and z -velocities may be excluded with minimal impact to surrogate accuracy, as well as spatial standard deviations of temporal standard deviations and

Figure 3.3: Scatter plots of surrogate results from the random forest training for low-speed shaft torque DELs (a, b, and c) and yaw bearing roll moment DELs (d, e, and f). Surrogates in (a) and (d) were constructed using all 108 available wind inputs but excluding nacelle yaw. Surrogates in (b) and (e) were constructed using all 108 available wind inputs and including nacelle yaw. Surrogates in (c) and (f) were constructed using the reduced number of inputs (34, including nacelle yaw). Each point in all plots is colored by the corresponding nacelle yaw (based on case and turbine number).

spatial means of temporal absolute maximums.

Figure 3.4 shows the performance of the selected best-fit surrogate using 34 inputs (including nacelle yaw) for selected output channels. These are the bending moments DELs for: (a) blade root pitching; (b) low-speed shaft 0°; (c) yaw bearing yaw; and (d) tower base yaw. Strong performance is seen from all output channels, including those not shown in the plot (blade root in-plane and out-of-plane, low-speed shaft 90°, yaw bearing pitch and roll, and tower base pitch and roll moments).

Figure 3.4: Scatter plots of surrogate results from the random forest training for all outputs. Each point in all plots is colored by the corresponding nacelle yaw (based on case and turbine number).

3.1.3 POD-based surrogate approach (DTU (3))

Figure 3.5 presents the test set predictions from the POD-based surrogate models, comparing the predicted load values against the Fast.Farm results. Each subplot corresponds to a specific load component: Tower Base Side-Side (TBSS), Tower Base Fore-Aft (TBFA), Blade Root Out-of-Plane (BROoP), and Blade Root In-Plane (BRIP) Bending Moments. The RMSPE is reported for each load surrogate, indicating prediction accuracy. The results demonstrate that the POD-based FCNN surrogates accurately approximate load responses, with exceptionally low RMSPE

values for BRIP (0.08%) and BROoP (1.02%), suggesting near-perfect predictions. The TBFA (1.42%) and TBSS (3.71%) surrogates show slightly higher errors but are within the seed-to-seed uncertainty of wind turbine simulations (Tibaldi et al., 2014, Liew and Larsen, 2022).

Figure 3.5: Test set predictions from POD-based surrogate models for different load components

The surrogate models were trained with a specific set of input parameters as described in section 2.4. Future work could include feature exploration to assess whether incorporating additional inputs enhances the accuracy. Additionally, a sensitivity analysis could be conducted as future work to quantify the influence of each input parameter on the predicted loads, providing deeper insights into surrogate model's behavior.

3.1.4 Gaussian process surrogate approach (TUD (4))

The validation results of the Gaussian process load surrogate model are presented in Figure 3.6. The load channels that were considered were the blade root flap-wise bending moment, the low-speed shaft out-of-plane bending moment, the yaw bearing fore-aft bending moment, and the tower base fore-aft bending moment. The first three components show similar prediction accuracies, with only small differences between the training and test sets. In the case of the tower base, the test set performs notably worse, which could indicate overfitting to the training data. The surrogate model performs well overall, although the RMSPE for every component is slightly higher than for the other load surrogate models. We believe this is partially the result of the smaller dataset and the lower number of turbulence seeds. Additional simulations are currently underway to increase the size of the datasets used for training and validation.

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Figure 3.6: Scatter plots of the training (red) and test (blue) data compared to predictions of the Gaussian process model based on the training and test input data.

3.2 Parametric study on best design choices for a load surrogate

While Sect. 3.1 showed the key performance indicators for the selected best-fit proposed load surrogates, this section extends on a parametric study to see the impact of some surrogate design choices on their performances.

3.2.1 Choice and number of inputs to the surrogate to map the local flow field

Concerning the sector-based surrogates (approach (1)), Figures 3.7 and 3.8 illustrate the significant advantage of using more than simple rotor-averaged quantities (“SAIQs 1”). For the blade root DEL, there is a clear benefit for the surrogate to be informed about left/right difference, as there is a huge improvement going from “SAIQs 2A” to “SAIQs 2B”. This is due to the effect of partial-wake overlap, which predominantly drives the blade root DELs (with an asymmetric effect as can be seen in Figure 3.14). For the tower base DEL, there is a gradual improvement of the surrogate by increasing the number of sectors. This is attributed to the more spatially-resolved mapping of the turbulence, which is driving this DEL. Also due to partial-wake effects, and for convergence of quantities, it appears beneficial for the surrogate to know detailed local turbulence instead than one representative turbulence intensity.

Globally, utilizing four or six sectors across the rotor disk strikes an effective balance between model complexity and surrogate accuracy. Further increasing the number of sectors does not offer significant improvements in surrogate performance in this case. In fact, a higher discrepancy between the training and validation subsets is observed when using six to eight sectors, suggesting overfitting of the training dataset due to an excessive number of inputs. However if more complex inflow effects, such as low-level jets, were to be tested, a higher number of sectors might

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Figure 3.7: *Sector-based surrogates (approach 1)*: RMSPE of for the blade root DEL evaluated for various input choices. The choice of sector-averaged inflow quantities (SAIQs) across the rotor disk are schematized above each bar. For each case, average wind speeds and turbulence intensities are computed for the delimited sectors.

Figure 3.8: *Sector-based surrogates (approach 1)*: RMSPE of for the tower base DEL evaluated for various input choices. The choice of sector-averaged inflow quantities (SAIQs) across the rotor disk is schematized above each bar. For each case, average wind speeds and turbulence intensities are computed for the delimited sectors.

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prove more beneficial.

Concerning the POD-based surrogate (approach (3)), Figure 3.9 presents the RMSPE for both training and testing datasets evaluated using an increasing number of POD modes. As expected, the test set exhibits a slightly higher prediction error compared to the training set, reflecting the model's generalisation capability. The comparison highlights the impact of POD modes on the accuracy of the surrogate model in predicting the projected blade root DEL. A significant improvement in accuracy is observed between 1 and 3 modes, where the error drops very quickly, suggesting that even with just a few modes, the surrogate model is able to capture dominant flow structures influencing blade root DEL. However, adding more modes beyond this point leads to gradual refinements rather than drastic improvements. Any number of modes between 5 and 7 seems to be a reasonable choice for the Projected Blade root DEL surrogate, offering a good balance between capturing essential features and generalising well to unseen test datasets. In the work of Liew et al., 2023, 10 modes were used, although 99.99% of the variance was captured with just 6 modes. However, the study does not provide a specific justification for choosing 10 modes, nor does it analyze the impact of the number of modes on the model's predictive performance. Moreover, comparing Figure 3.9, where surrogates rely on POD-based inputs, and Figure 3.7, which uses sector averaged inputs, reveals that the POD-based approach converges faster. The slower convergence of sector-averaged models can be due to averaging of inflow along the blade span. This averaging process seems to reduce the model's ability to capture localized variation, consequently requiring more sectors to achieve the same level of accuracy as the POD-based approach.

For approaches 1-3, the wind velocity data that is used in computing the surrogate inputs is taken directly from the blade nodes of the turbine model. The IEA 22MW turbine, used for generating the Shell dataset, has 50 blade nodes (Zahle et al., 2024). However, it is possible to generate the input statistics using fewer blade nodes. To determine the impact on surrogate performance based on the number of blade nodes used to generate the input data, the input statistics were computed from the same dataset, but using a different number of blade nodes. The number of blade nodes and corresponding locations are shown in Figure 3.10. While this study was done using approach 2, it is expected that the results apply to other approaches that directly use blade node wind velocity data, such as approach 1.

The percent differences of RMSE values for all output channels as a function of the number of blade stations used to calculate inflow statistics are shown in Figure 3.11. From these results, there seems to be no clear trend across all output channels. LSS and IP blade-root bending moment results show improved performance with fewer blade nodes, while the remaining output channels show generally reduced performance, especially when only 5 blade nodes are included. However,

Figure 3.9: *POD-based surrogates (approach 3)*: RMSPE for training and testing datasets as a function of the number of POD modes in the surrogate model. The figure illustrates the impact of the number of modes on the surrogate model's performance.

Figure 3.10: *Velocity inflow slices-based surrogates (approach 2)*: Blade node locations for computing wind velocity statistics used as surrogate inputs.

the overall impact is relatively minimal, with the largest percent difference being 6.92% and an average of 0.3%. Additionally, there was negligible impact on the correlation coefficient for all results (maximum change of 0.01). Despite the lack

of a clear trend, the reasonably low impact on the number of blade nodes on surrogate performance is encouraging. The low-fidelity models that could eventually make use of these surrogate models likely do not have high resolution for the wind data. Therefore, the limited impact bodes well for including the proposed surrogate models in such low-fidelity models.

Figure 3.11: *Velocity inflow slices-based surrogates (approach 2)*: Percent difference of RMSE for all output channels as a function of the number of blade stations used to calculate inflow statistics.

3.2.2 Number of training points and turbulent seeds

An important design consideration for load surrogates is determining the required number of training points. As data-driven approaches, the performance of the surrogates is expected to converge once the training set adequately captures all relevant combinations of input-output relationships. Furthermore, due to the inherent stochasticity of both the local inflow characteristics and the DELs, the inputs and the outputs of the surrogate are averaged over a certain number of turbulent seed realizations. Increasing the number of seeds allows to have smoother data for the surrogates to learn from, reducing the uncertainty due to turbulence. Another design choice for load surrogates is then to know how many turbulent seeds are necessary for converged performance. IEC standards recommend 6 turbulent seeds for single turbine simulations (IEC 61400-1, 2019), but it has been shown that on the farm level, wake effects add turbulent uncertainty (Liew and Larsen, 2022).

Concerning the Gaussian process-based surrogates (approach (4)), Figure 3.12 shows the model's prediction performance for an increasing quantity of training

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points. The prediction error of the blade root DELs is still decreasing with the current available dataset. A similar trend is visible for the tower base DELs, although at a slower rate. Based on these trends, we expect the model predictions to improve after adding simulation data with different turbulent seeds. Compared to the other sector-based surrogate approach from TUM, it seems that the Gaussian process model requires a larger amount of training data to achieve similar performance.

Figure 3.12: *Gaussian-process-based surrogates (approach 4)*: RMSPE convergence of the Gaussian process load surrogate model comparing training data (blue line) with test data (red line) for an increasing amount of training data.

For the sector-based surrogates (approach (1)), Figures 3.13 (a) and (c) show that using approximately 20% of the dataset (equivalent to 2,050 simulation cases) is sufficient to achieve good and generalizable surrogate performance. Figures 3.13 (b) and (d) demonstrate that around 12 turbulent seeds are adequate to obtain converged performance of the trained load surrogate model.

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Figure 3.13: *Sector-based surrogates (approach 1)*: RMSPE for the blade root DEL ((a) and (b)) and for the tower base DEL ((c) and (d)) for an increasing number of training cases ((a) and (c)) and for an increasing number of turbulent seeds ((b) and (d)). In all the panels, the shaded area represents the minimum and maximum values from various randomized orderings, while the solid lines indicate the mean values. All these results use four sectors ("SAIQs 4A" strategy) applied across the rotor disk. The results in panels (a) and (c) use 24 turbulent seeds, while the results in panel (b) and (d) use 50% of the cases for training.

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3.3 Demonstration of the surrogates capabilities

All presented location-agnostic and control-oriented surrogates aim to capture the trends of DELs for various layout and wind farm control configurations. While Sect. 3.1 and Sect. 3.2 presented key performance metrics across the whole training and testing data sets, this section deep dives into showcasing the ability of the surrogates to predict fatigue loads for any turbine in certain specific configurations.

3.3.1 Capturing fatigue load trends by unaccounted external parameters

All the presented surrogates are based solely on the knowledge of local inflow quantities as well as local control set-points for a certain turbine. That is, the surrogate is not informed of the possible presence of upstream turbines, wind direction, or farm-level control. This is necessary to ensure that the surrogates are universally applicable to any wind farm layout and farm control actions. It is here demonstrated that this idea of location-agnostic surrogate models is in fact working. To do so, the performance of the surrogates to predict the variation of loads due to unaccounted external parameters (“farm-level” parameters, that the surrogates are uninformed of).

Concerning the sector-based surrogates (approach (1)), Figure 3.14 presents the surrogate predictions of DELs for three selected farm trends. These cases originate from the same FAST.Farm dataset based on three turbines: WT1 (upstream), WT2 (middle), and WT3 (downstream). The ambient average wind speed is 10 m/s with 6% turbulence intensity. The spacing between turbines is $6D$.

In a baseline case, the three turbines are aligned with the wind, without yaw misalignments, and at full rated power. The left column in Fig. 3.14 displays the effect of changing wind direction. The middle column illustrates the effect of misaligning the front turbine, steering its wake away from the downstream turbines. Lastly, the right column depicts the effect of curtailing the front turbine, reducing the speed deficit in its wake.

The surrogate model exclusively receives information on local SAWs, SATIs, and control set-points. Nevertheless, it predicts all the DELs with remarkable accuracy across the various farm configurations in Fig. 3.14. In the case of the upstream turbine WT1, SAWs and SATIs remain constant. The surrogate effectively anticipates changes in its DELs based on the varying local control set-points (yaw, rotor speed, and blade pitch angle). Conversely, deliberate variations in control set-points are not introduced for the downstream turbines WT2 and WT3, as they are maintained in maximum power mode. The surrogate accurately forecasts changes in their DELs based on fluctuations in SAWs and SATIs caused by wakes.

While results on Figure 3.14 use the surrogate trained on a very large dataset for the IEA 3.4MW, similar results can be seen for the new surrogate on the IEA 22MW

Figure 3.14: Surrogate predictions of DEL trends for an array of three IEA 3.4MW turbines by unaccounted external parameters. Left column: DELs vs. wind direction. Middle column: DELs vs. yaw misalignment of the front turbine. Right column: DELs vs. curtailment of the front turbine. Each row corresponds to a load channel. In these cases the turbines are spaced $6D$ and the mean ambient wind speed is $10m/s$ with a TI of 6%. Solid lines: actual DEL values. Dashed lines: surrogate predictions of DELs.

turbine in Figures 3.15 and 3.16. In this case, only results of DELs predictions by wind direction are shown (as cases with wind farm control actions are still being simulated). Figure 3.15 shows a case with three IEA 22MW turbines spaced $6D$,

mean wind speed of 10 m/s and TI 6%. Figure 3.16 shows a case with three IEA 22MW turbines spaced $4D$, mean wind speed of 8 m/s and TI of 12%. While it was seen on Figure 3.2 that the scatter of this new surrogate for the IEA 22MW turbine is a bit larger, due to the low number of training points at this stage, remarkable match of the DELs trends by wind direction is observed in both Figure 3.15 and Figure 3.16, based solely on the knowledge of local SAWS, SATI and control set-points. These results demonstrate that the proposed surrogate approach is suitable for any turbine type (even being completely different from the aero-servo-elastic design perspective).

Figure 3.15: Surrogate predictions of DEL trends for an array of three IEA 22MW turbines by wind direction (an unaccounted external parameter). In these cases the turbines are spaced $6D$ and the mean ambient wind speed is 10 m/s with a TI of 6%. Solid lines: actual DEL values. Dashed lines: surrogate predictions of DELs.

The results of a case study for the Gaussian process-based surrogates (approach (4)) are presented in Figure 3.17. This case study considers the wake of a turbine operating in free-stream at a velocity of $U_\infty = 8\text{ m/s}$ and average TI of 4%. The upstream turbine was operated using three different control methods, consisting of baseline operation, the helix method with a pitch amplitude of $A_{\text{pitch}} = 3.5^\circ$, and wake steering with a yaw misalignment of $\gamma = 25^\circ$. The surrogate model predicted the loads of a turbine located at a distance of $5D$ downstream and operating under baseline control for different wind directions.

Figure 3.17 shows that the surrogate model captures the load trends quite well

Figure 3.16: Surrogate predictions of DEL trends for an array of three IEA 22MW turbines by wind direction (an unaccounted external parameter). In these cases the turbines are spaced $4D$ and the mean ambient wind speed is $8m/s$ with a TI of 12%. Solid lines: actual DEL values. Dashed lines: surrogate predictions of DELs.

and that most of the actual DELs lie within the 95% confidence interval of the load predictions. For the blade root DELs, all control cases show two distinguishable peaks that are the result of partial wake overlap. When the helix is applied at the upstream turbine, the loads at the considered turbine increase slightly in the fully aligned case. Wake steering shows a slight decrease in blade root loads overall, as well as a displacement of the peaks. The trends for the shaft and yaw bearing loads are quite similar. Both the helix method and wake steering slightly increase the overall loading for most wind directions. When considering the tower base DELs, we notice a wider peak for the baseline case, while for the other cases the peak load is slightly higher. From this study, we conclude that the helix method generally leads to an increase in fatigue loading at downstream turbines, whereas wake steering can either improve or worsen the loads of the downstream turbine depending on the alignment of the two turbines with the wind direction.

Figure 3.17: Validation results of the Gaussian process load surrogate models for a range of wind directions and different wind farm flow control methods. The predictions consider the case of a turbine operating downstream of a *controlled* turbine at a distance of $5D$. The shaded area around the load predictions indicates the 95% confidence interval of the load surrogate predictions. For the helix and wake steering cases, the upstream turbine was operating with a pitch amplitude of $A_\theta = 3.5^\circ$ and a yaw misalignment of $\gamma = 25^\circ$, respectively.

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3.3.2 Capturing fatigue loads for an arbitrary wind farm and control actions

To validate the desired broad applicability of the load surrogate for layout or farm control applications, its capabilities are tested using a different wind farm configuration with various farm control set-points. Indeed, the surrogate was trained using a dataset built from simulating an array of three wind turbines. But it is meant to be applicable for any turbine regardless of its position, and for any wind farm layout configuration. The only requirement is that the wind turbine model remains the same. Furthermore, the surrogate was trained on a certain set of control set-points. But it is meant to be applicable for any possible desired set-points, as long as they lie in the training range.

A wind farm comprising five IEA 3.4MW turbines (Bortolotti et al., 2019) serves as a new testing case. Figure 3.18 illustrates the layout that was artificially selected to include various spacings between turbines and various degrees of wake impingement. WT1 is in free stream. WT2, WT3, and WT4 are in different partial wakes. WT5 is in a full wake. The simulations are conducted with FAST.Farm including wake-added turbulence (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021; Kretschmer et al., 2021). 24 turbulent seeds are run for each case. The ambient average wind speed is 10 m/s with 6% turbulence intensity. The inputs required by the surrogate model are extracted from FAST.Farm as explained in Sect. 2.3.2. The sector-based surrogate (approach (1)) using the “SAIQs 4A” strategy is used in these results.

Twenty-one different cases of farm control set-points were run to test the ability of the surrogate to capture their effects on loads. The set-points of WT1, WT2, and WT3 were collectively varied. Their yaw misalignment angles were varied between $-30^\circ : 10^\circ : +30^\circ$, while curtailment levels were set to 100%, 80% and 60% of rated power.

Figure 3.18: Visualization of the layout used for testing of the surrogate. The yaw angle convention is indicated next to WT1. The background is a snapshot of the instantaneous velocity field at hub height using FAST.Farm (Jonkman and Shaler, 2021).

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Figure 3.19 compares the actual DELs with those predicted by the surrogate. The figure includes data for all five turbines (organized by columns) and four load channels (organized by rows). Overall, the surrogate demonstrates a very good ability in predicting the amplitudes and variations of all DELs for various control strategies. WT1 yields the best match, as wake effects do not influence it. The surrogate effectively captures the noteworthy effects of both yawing and curtailing WT1 on its fatigue. Curtailing the turbine mitigates the increase in blade root DELs for negative yaw misalignments. It also reduces the shaft and yaw bearing DELs for all yaw angles. However, for high misalignment amplitudes, tower base DELs in curtailed operation appear to be slightly larger than those in fully rated operation.

The surrogate also performs well at predicting DEL variations for all the downstream turbines experiencing complex wakes and control interactions. The tower base DELs remain relatively low even for partially-waked turbines, but exhibit a significant increase in full wake situations. This is evident for WT5, which is consistently positioned in the full wake of WT3. A similar trend is seen for WT2 and WT3 for yaw angles that deflect the wake of WT1 fully towards them. The wake-added turbulence is presumably driving this phenomenon. The shaft, yaw bearings, and the blade root DELs are more sensitive to partial wake impingements, exhibiting asymmetric effects.

The surrogate shows a slightly reduced ability to predict the shaft and yaw bearing DELs of WT2 and WT3. This could be attributed to the intricate coupling between the varying wake of WT1 affecting WT2 and WT3, and the fluctuations in yaw misalignments and curtailment levels for these turbines. Nevertheless, globally it can be said that the surrogate successfully captures reasonably well the complex variation in DELs influenced by wind farm control, even under different wake overlaps coupled with control actions.

Figure 3.19: Sector-based surrogate (approach (1)) predictions of DELs trends for the new testing wind farm. Turbines are organized by columns, whereas load channels by rows. The yaw misalignment angles of WT1, 2 and 3 are collectively changed on the x-axis, while the colors blue, red and yellow respectively correspond to curtailment levels of 100%, 80% and 60% of rated power for WT1, 2 and 3 collectively. Solid lines: actual DEL values. Dashed lines: surrogate predictions of DELs.

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4 Conclusion

This deliverable has presented the development and validation of advanced load surrogate models within the SUDOCO research project, aiming to enhance the state-of-the-art in wind turbine fatigue load prediction. Compared to prior work, these surrogate models offer significant improvements in terms of generalizability, computational efficiency, and applicability to wind farm control strategies. While surrogate models prior to the SUDOCO projects were often site-specific and struggled with wake-induced and control-induced effects on fatigue loads, the SUDOCO surrogate models are location-agnostic and control-oriented. This enables their deployment across a wide range of wind farm layouts while incorporating the effects of wake steering, static and dynamic induction control, and varying inflow conditions.

Throughout this work, four different surrogate modeling approaches have been explored, each designed to address the challenges of fatigue load prediction in wind farms. While the general objectives and implementation of these four surrogates are similar, the first three approaches mostly differ by the choice of reduced-order quantities to map the local inflow at each rotor disk: sector-averaged wind speeds and TI for TUM's approach, inflow velocity slices for Shell's approach and POD of the inflow for DTU's approach. The choice of surrogate function also differentiates these approaches, with respectively shallow ANN, random forest and deep ANN. The fourth surrogate approach, developed by TU Delft, also uses sector-averaged wind speeds and TI, and the surrogate is formulated as a Gaussian process. Notably, this fourth approach mainly differentiates itself by its scope of application, as it is aimed to being used for advanced dynamic induction control strategies (while the former three are bounded for application to wake steering and static induction control).

The results demonstrated that all four surrogate models achieved high levels of predictive accuracy, with very high correlation coefficients (R^2) and low root-mean-square percentage errors (RMSPE) across both the training and the testing data sets. The sectors-based and the velocity slice-based approaches present similar performances. They are judged to be a good trade-off between accuracy and complexity. The POD-based approach demonstrated higher performances (lower RMSPE), at the cost of a slightly more complex implementation in the perspective of linking the surrogate with a steady-state reduced order inflow model. Finally, the Gaussian process-based surrogate showed a bit reduced performances compared to the other surrogates, which can be attributed to the added complexity of its larger application range with dynamic induction control. Furthermore, it requires

more computational resources, so this last surrogate was trained on fewer points and fewer turbulent seeds. Overall, all surrogate approaches demonstrated their suitability. This comparison does not discard any approach, but rather it highlights that different surrogates can be built for different purposes, balancing between complexity and accuracy.

A parametric study was conducted to determine some optimal design choices for surrogate modeling. This analysis highlighted key insights such as the minimum number of inputs required to accurately capture the effect of the local inflow spatio-temporal variation on the DELs. While it is hard to directly compare the different approaches (number of sectors, number of blade stations, and number of POD modes), the main common finding is that while single rotor-averaged quantities are not sufficient to capture DELs, a finite number of parameters proves sufficient for convergence of the surrogate estimates. This is an important and very useful finding, as it means that load surrogates can be built on a reasonably small number of inputs and still capture all relevant variations of DELs. The number of training points necessary to reach convergence of the surrogate was also investigated for two surrogate approaches. It also shows that a certain amount of training points is sufficient to capture all possible cases based on a very large dataset. Finally, the study also confirmed the importance of including various turbulence seeds in the training phase (12 seeds being recommended) to ensure converged statistics and stable surrogate reliability.

The capabilities of these surrogate models were further demonstrated by their ability to accurately replicate fatigue load trends under diverse wind farm layouts, environmental conditions, and wind farm control actions. This demonstrated their potential as essential tools for optimizing wind farm operations while considering structural loads.

While the surrogate models developed in this study represent a significant advancement in load modeling, several challenges remain: the inclusion of ultimate loads (which should be straightforward with current approaches), the inclusion of the complex effects of floating loads, and the effect of low-frequency fatigue cycles. While these are not judged to be fundamental at this stage for the current application of the developed surrogates for wind farm flow control, they are certainly fascinating paths for future improvements. Additionally, these surrogates were developed and tested solely in simulation environments. Experimental reduced-scaled and full-scaled demonstrations of these surrogates would be crucial for their future industrial application.

However, the key natural next step is the integration of these load surrogates with reduced-order inflow models to enable fast optimization of wind farm control strategies, including the consideration of fatigue loads alongside the energy yield. As part of the SUDOCO project, these load surrogates should complement other

data-driven models regarding the economic value (time-varying market prices) and environmental value (time-varying potential for the displacements of CO₂ emissions on the electrical grid) of wind farm control (see dedicated deliverables D3.2 and D3.3, respectively). This holistic approach will be a fundamental component of the SUDOCO project's vision for the "*Control Room of the Future*," where advanced data-driven tools will support wind farm operators in achieving a balance between energy yield, structural reliability, market competitiveness, and the displacements of CO₂ emissions on the electrical grid, optimizing both the economic and environmental performances of future offshore wind farms.

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